

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

Name : Laifa Farihah

Student ID Number : P1_J0308211016XTO_ECREPORT

Vocational School Analysis Class (IKN-Science Fishery)

Object;

Laifa Farihah_Potret Pejuang Pendidikan Dalam Film “Sokola Rimba”_My Analysis

Background and Analysis

Abstract

Education works for upgrading intelligence intellectual and character in each human, education must also through a proper learning process as well as adequate from various aspects as well as corner easy view participant educate for could understand learning by maximum. So with this, a learning model that includes strategies, methods, techniques, and tactics should be arranged as well as possible. This “Sokola Rimba” movie is a film that has education and values humanity which aired in 2013. Research this aim for describe in detail the synopsis of the film " Sokola Rimba " and describes draft liberating education. Study this use method qualitative. The subject in the study is a film work entitled " Sokola Rimba " overall, the Method of data collection used is based on observation on film as well studies literature. Study this produce values about the struggle as well as existing humanity in figure Butet. Because for him important education is education that makes them ready to face pressure must change they face it and everyone deserves to get proper education.

CONCLUSION

The whole movie “Sokola Rimba” is a description of education fighters in the Jungle Village (Manurung, 2012). This movie is an Educational and humanitarian film which at its core is give education to people in the Rimba interior. From the start until the end story, will serve plot story figure Butet as warrior education in teaching in the jungle. Furthermore, by In general, the film " Sokola Rimba" also tells the story of about first struggles Rimba children as figures Nyungsang Bungo, Beindah, and Nengkabau no only Butet course. Struggle they in-demand knowledge so that the fool that happened to them and the Rimba people other not occur again, and fight to throw people away known who want rob Forest them. Second, based on results analysis could declare that not only limited entertainment film works only, but also works that can give reflection and reference related implementation teaching program activities in villages that can be realized in schools remote need power teacher.

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

Because society with the background behind very less education sufficient and very necessary accompaniment from other society more able. Accompaniment can also be given through supplies understandings that are useful application by straight away (Musasia, et al, 2012).

Article/Media/Literacy Resources based Qustions:

1) Is it Available data or information to answer it,

Ya. Dalam artikel tersebut terdapat berbagai informasi terkait pendidikan yang ada di pedalaman.

2) Is the data or information is obtained through scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests,

Ya. Data serta informasi tersebut diperoleh melalui observasi pada film “Sokola Rimba”.

3) Does it meet the originality requirements, identified through previous research mapping (state of the arts),

Ya. Karena diketahui sudah melalui pemetaan penelitian terdahulu terbukti dengan adanya berbagai macam judul yang hampir sama.

4) Does it make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science,

Tidak terlalu, karena artikel tersebut lebih mempresentasikan terkait isu social dan pendidikan.

5) Does it regard controversial and unique issues that are currently happening,

Tidak. Bukan isu yang sedang terjadi, namun isu yang dari dulu telah ada dan sampai sekarang belum kunjung usai.

6) The problem requires an answer and an immediate solution, but the answer is not yet known to the general public, and

Isu tersebut sudah mendapat jawaban serta solusi namun masih belum terealisasi.

7) The problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest (field of study) and ability.

Tidak. Isu tidak terlalu rumit dan dapat selesai jika sudah terealisasi dengan baik

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

8) What developments or shifts were taking place at the time the event occurred,

Pendidikan di pedalaman sedikit mengalami perkembangan dengan hadirnya seorang sosok pejuang pendidikan.

9) What are the benefits of this research for the development of science and society at large in the future?

Penelitian ini bermanfaat agar masyarakat serta pemerintah tahu dengan keadaan pendidikan di pedalaman, dan dapat merealisasikan pemerataan pendidikan yang ada di Indonesia

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

Bibliography and Recommended Papers for

References

- Achrol, R. S., & Kotler, P. (2012). Frontiers of the marketing paradigm in the third millennium. *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, 40(1), 35-52.
- Aguiar, M., Mathieson, C., & Pearce, L. (Eds.). (2019). *Mobilities, literature, culture*. Springer Nature.
- Allen, R. M., & Anderson, R. D. L. (2016). *The Arts*.
- Altman, R. (2021). 3. A Semantic/Syntactic Approach to film genre. In *Film genre reader IV* (pp. 27-41). University of Texas Press.
- Astuti, A. D. (2015). BECOMING EUROPEANIZED “NATIVE” IN ANDREA HIRATA’S THE LASKAR PELANGI QUARTET. Sanata Dharma University.
- Bateman, J., & Schmidt, K. H. (2013). *Multimodal film analysis: How films mean*. Routledge.
- Bednarek, M. (2015). Corpus-assisted multimodal discourse analysis of television and film narratives. In *Corpora and discourse studies* (pp. 63-87). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- Bellour, R. (2000). *The analysis of film*. Indiana University Press.
- Benshoff, H. (2015). *Film and television analysis: An introduction to methods, theories, and approaches*. Routledge.
- Bittau, F., Potamialis, C., Togay, M., Abbas, A., Isherwood, P. J., Bowers, J. W., & Walls, J. M. (2018). Analysis and optimisation of the glass/TCO/MZO stack for thin film CdTe solar cells. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 187, 15-22.
- Bostrom, N. (2020). Human genetic enhancements: a transhumanist perspective. In *The Ethics of Sports Technologies and Human Enhancement* (pp. 339-352). Routledge.
- Bostrom, N., & Yudkowsky, E. (2018). The ethics of artificial intelligence. In *Artificial intelligence safety and security* (pp. 57-69). Chapman and Hall/CRC.
- Brinkmann, S. (2014). Unstructured and semi-structured interviewing. *The Oxford handbook of qualitative research*, 277-299.
- Buda, I. K., & Payuyasa, I. N. (2020). Pendidikan yang memerdekakan dalam film “sokola rimba”. *Gorga: Jurnal Seni Rupa*, 9(2), 247-255.

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

- Carr, D. (2019). Methodology, representation, and games. *Games and Culture*, 14(7-8), 707-723.
- Collewaert, V., Anseel, F., Crommelinck, M., De Beuckelaer, A., & Vermeire, J. (2016). When passion fades: Disentangling the temporal dynamics of entrepreneurial passion for founding. *Journal of Management Studies*, 53(6), 966-995.
- Condon, W. S., & Ogston, W. D. (1966). Sound film analysis of normal and pathological behavior patterns. *Journal of nervous and mental disease*.
- Eralieva, A. E. ROLE OF TRANSLATION FOR HUMANITY. CULTURAL AND LINGUISTIC BARRIERS. *Главный редактор*, 60.
- Eriksson, P., & Kovalainen, A. (2015). *Qualitative methods in business research: A practical guide to social research*. Sage.
- Estrada, L. M., Hielscher, E., Koolen, M., Olesen, C. G., Noordegraaf, J., & Blom, J. (2017). Film analysis as annotation: Exploring current tools. *Moving Image: The Journal of the Association of Moving Image Archivists*, 17(2), 40-70.
- Firmansyah, M. B. (2018). Multimodal conception in learning. *ISLLAC: Journal of Intensive Studies on Language, Literature, Art, and Culture*, 2(1), 40-44.
- Franco, A., Magnani, A., & Maio, D. (2020). A multimodal approach for human activity recognition based on skeleton and RGB data. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 131, 293-299.
- Freeman, M. (2015). *Rewriting the self: History, memory, narrative*. Routledge.
- García, E., & Weiss, E. (2020). COVID-19 and Student Performance, Equity, and US Education Policy: Lessons from Pre-Pandemic Research to Inform Relief, Recovery, and Rebuilding. *Economic Policy Institute*.
- Geiger, J., & Rutsky, R. L. (Eds.). (2013). *Film analysis: A Norton reader*. WW Norton & Company.
- Henseler, C. (2021). Finding Humanity. *The Scholar as Human: Research and Teaching for Public Impact*, 129.
- Heryanto, A. (2014). *Identity and pleasure: The politics of Indonesian screen culture*. NUS Press.
- Humphreys, D. (2012). *Logjam: Deforestation and the crisis of global governance*. Routledge.

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

- Ismaili, J., & Ibrahim, E. H. O. (2017). Mobile learning as alternative to assistive technology devices for special needs students. *Education and Information Technologies*, 22(3), 883-899.
- Jahn, M. (2003). *A guide to narratological film analysis. Poems, Plays, and Prose: A Guide to the Theory of Literary Genres*, 2.
- Joy, B. (2020). Why the future doesn't need us: Our most powerful 21st-century technologies-robotics, genetic engineering, and nanotech-are threatening to make humans an endangered species. In *Emerging Technologies: Ethics, Law and Governance* (pp. 47-63). Routledge.
- Jurriëns, E. (2016). 'TV or Not TV': Spelling the Indonesian Media with Veven Sp. Wardhana. *Bijdragen tot de taal-, land-en volkenkunde/Journal of the Humanities and Social Sciences of Southeast Asia*, 172(1), 33-65.
- Kaufmann, W. A. (2013). *Nietzsche: Philosopher, psychologist, antichrist (Vol. 3)*. Princeton University Press.
- Kendrick, M. (2016). *Literacy and multimodality across global sites*. Routledge.
- Kozlarek, O. (2015). Introduction: Crossing Borders, Reaching Humanity. In Octavio Paz (pp. 9-16). transcript-Verlag.
- Kozol, J. (2012). *Savage inequalities: Children in America's schools*. Crown.
- Kuśnierek, A. (2016). The role of music and songs in teaching English vocabulary to students. *World Scientific News*, 1(43), 1-55.
- Lo, H. F., Wu, I. W., & Ni, C. C. (2018, July). Representation of Memory in Design for Humanity. In *International Conference on Cross-Cultural Design* (pp. 43-57). Springer, Cham.
- Love, B. L. (2019). *We want to do more than survive: Abolitionist teaching and the pursuit of educational freedom*. Beacon Press.
- Magnusson, P., & Godhe, A. L. (2019). Multimodality in Language Education--Implications for Teaching. *Designs for Learning*, 11(1), 127-137.
- Mailloux, S. (2018). *Interpretive conventions*. Cornell University Press.. Interpretive conventions. Cornell University Press.
- Manurung, B. (2012). *The jungle school*. Xlibris Corporation.
- Manurung, B. (2019). 13 'Normalising'the Orang Rimba: between mainstreaming, marginalising and respecting indigenous culture. *ISEAS Library Cataloguing-in-Publication Data*, 232.

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

- Manurung, B. (2019). 13 'Normalising'the Orang Rimba: between mainstreaming, marginalising and respecting indigenous culture. ISEAS Library Cataloguing-in-Publication Data, 232.
- Marmot, M., Allen, J., Bell, R., Bloomer, E., & Goldblatt, P. (2012). WHO European review of social determinants of health and the health divide. *The Lancet*, 380(9846), 1011-1029.
- McLynn, F. (2013). *Crime and punishment in eighteenth century England*. Routledge.
- Mulatsih, M. V. E., & Aurora, V. D. (2021). SELF-REGULATED LEARNING IN BUTET MANURUNG'S THE JUNGLE SCHOOL. *IJiet (International Journal of Indonesian Education and Teaching)*, 5(2), 148-157.
- Mulatsih, M. V. E., & Aurora, V. D. (2021). SELF-REGULATED LEARNING IN BUTET MANURUNG'S THE JUNGLE SCHOOL. *IJiet (International Journal of Indonesian Education and Teaching)*, 5(2), 148-157.
- Musasia, A. M., Abacha, O. A., & Biyoyo, M. E. (2012). Effect of Practical Work in Physics on Girls' Performance, Attitude change and Skills acquisition in the form two-form three Secondary Schools' transition in Kenya. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(23), 151-166.
- Noddings, N. (2018). *Philosophy of education*. Routledge.
- Pattiwael, A. S. (2019). Literature for Developing Student's Humanity Awareness. In *Journal International Seminar on Languages, Literature, Arts, and Education (ISLLAE)* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 79-88).
- Plate, L. (2015). How to do things with literature in the digital age: Anne Carson's *Nox*, multimodality, and the ethics of bookishness. *Contemporary Women's Writing*, 9(1), 93-111.
- Purwanto, E. (2017). *Challenges of the Social Forestry Program in Indonesia*.
- Rabinow, P. (2016). *Reflections on fieldwork in Morocco*. University of California Press.
- Rodrik, D. (2015). *Economics rules: The rights and wrongs of the dismal science*. WW Norton & Company.
- Rudolph, F. (2021). *The American college and university: A history*. Plunkett Lake Press.
- Sensoy, O., & DiAngelo, R. (2017). *Is everyone really equal?: An introduction to key concepts in social justice education*. Teachers College Press.
- Setiawan, Y. B., & Rahmawati, S. (Eds.). (2020). *Emerging Trends in Psychology, Law, Communication Studies, Culture, Religion, and Literature in the Global Digital*

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

Revolution: Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Social Sciences Series: Psychology, Law, Communication Studies, Culture, Religion, and Literature (SOSCIS 2019), July 10 2019, Semarang Indonesia. Routledge.

Sheridan, T. B. (2016). Human–robot interaction: status and challenges. *Human factors*, 58(4), 525-532.

Simanjuntak Irma Rasita Gloria, M. B. B. (2020). English Reading Literacies to Improve Values Among Teenagers. *SELTICS*, Vol 3 No 2 (2020) : Seltics Journal, 93–102. <https://ejournals.umma.ac.id/index.php/seltics/article/view/734/596>

Simanjuntak Irma Rasita Gloria; Resmayasari, Ira, M. B. B. (2020). Analysis of Song “Tanganku Na Metmet” by Using Translation Techniques into English. *UICELL*, No 4 (2020): UICELL Conference Proceedings 2020, 195–202. <https://journal.uhamka.ac.id/index.php/uicell/article/view/6276/2122>

Simanjuntak Irma Rasita Gloria; Resmayasari, Ira, M. B. B. (2021). ANALYSIS OF VIOLENCE IN CITY OF GOD FILM DIRECTED BY FERNANDO MEIRELLES. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, Vol 4 No 1 (2021): *Journal of Advanced English Studies*, 1–6. <http://sastra.unifa.ac.id/journal/index.php/jes/article/view/97/53>

Simanjuntak Marthin Steven, M. B. S. L. (2021). THE WOMAN IN THE BOOK OF KINGS (LITERARY STUDIES AND HERMENEUTICS). *UICELL*, No 5 (2021): UICELL Conference Proceedings 2021, 328–334. <https://journal.uhamka.ac.id/index.php/uicell/article/view/8364/2704>

Simanjuntak Muchlas; Setiadi, Samsi, M. B. S. (2021). THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MICROSOFT OFFICE 365 AS AN ONLINE ENGLISH LEARNING MEDIA. *UICELL*, No 5 (2021): UICELL Conference Proceedings 2021, 25–32. <https://journal.uhamka.ac.id/index.php/uicell/article/view/8286/2670>

Simanjuntak Zuriyati; Lustyantje, Ninuk, M. B. Z. (2022). METAMORPHIC ANALYSIS IN SONG LYRICS BATAK TOBA “JUJUNG GOARHI AMANG” (STUDY OF PORTRAY OF PARENTS). *PROJECT (Professional Journal of English Education)*, Vol 5, No 1 (2022): VOLUME 5 NUMBER 1, JANUARY 2022, 236–243. <https://journal.ikipsiliwangi.ac.id/index.php/project/article/view/10000/pdf>

Simanjuntak, M. B. (2020a). REPRESENTATION OF WISDOM IN THE BOOK OF PROVERBS WRITTEN BY SOLOMON. *SELTICS*, Vol 3 No 1 (2020): Seltics Journal, 33–40. <https://ejournals.umma.ac.id/index.php/seltics/article/view/543/404>

Simanjuntak, M. B. (2020b). THE EDUCATIONAL VALUES OF THE MAIN CHARACTER IN BEAUTIFUL MIND FILM. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED*

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

ENGLISH STUDIES, Vol 3 No 1 (2020): Journal of Advanced English Studies, 1–6.
<http://sastra.unifa.ac.id/journal/index.php/jes/article/view/83/42>

Simanjuntak, M. B. (2020c). THE EFFECTS OF INTEGRATION BETWEEN KURIKULUM 2013 AND CAMBRIDGE CURRICULUM IN ENGLISH (STUDY CASE TAKEN FROM SAINT PETER'S JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL). JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES, Vol 3 No 1 (2020): Journal of Advanced English Studies, 50–59. <http://sastra.unifa.ac.id/journal/index.php/jes/article/view/77/39>

Simanjuntak, M. B. (2021). METAMORPHIC ANALYSIS IN SONG LYRICS BATAK TOBA "AUT BOI NIAN" WRITTEN BY WERVIN PANGGABEAN. JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES, Vol 4 No 1 (2021): Journal of Advanced English Studies, 34–39.
<http://sastra.unifa.ac.id/journal/index.php/jes/article/view/99/56>

Simanjuntak, M. B., Suseno, M., Setiadi, S., Lustyantje, N., & Barus, I. R. G. R. G. (2022). Integration of Curricula (Curriculum 2013 and Cambridge Curriculum for Junior High School Level in Three Subjects) in Pandemic Situation. Ideas: Jurnal Pendidikan, Sosial, dan Budaya, 8(1), 77-86.

Soewondo, P., Ferrario, A., & Tahapary, D. L. (2013). Challenges in diabetes management in Indonesia: a literature review. Globalization and health, 9(1), 1-17.

Subanar, G. B. (2020). Soegija a Child of Bethlehem van Java: Biography of Mgr. Albertus Soegijapranata The First Indonesian Bishop. Sanata Dharma University Press.

Tanang, H., & Abu, B. (2014). Teacher Professionalism and Professional Development Practices in South Sulawesi, Indonesia. Journal of curriculum and teaching, 3(2), 25-42.

Van Manen, M. (2016). Researching lived experience: Human science for an action sensitive pedagogy. Routledge.

Wellek, R. (2018). The attack on literature and other essays. UNC Press Books.

Widjayanti, E. P. (2019). Building Humanity Values Through Maya Angelou's poems. In Journal International Seminar on Languages, Literature, Arts, and Education (ISLLAE) (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 143-148).

Winnicott, D. W. (2018). Mirror-role of mother and family in child development 1 (pp. 18-24). Routledge.

Wu, J., & Yan, Y. (2016, November). Study of humanity teaching model in higher vocational school Chinese teaching. In Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Management Science, Education Tecnology, Arts, Social Science and Economics (Vol. 85, pp. 1855-1858).